

The BIOSECURE Act 2.0: Balancing National Security and Biotech Innovation

Issue/problem

After failing to pass it earlier, the US Senate endorsed a revised BIOSECURE Act on October 10th as an [amendment](#) to the FY-2026 National Defense Authorization Act. The so-called “[BIOSECURE 2.0](#)” aims to restrict federally funded pharma/biotech work with designated Chinese “[biotechnology companies of concern](#).”

Description of the problem

The amendment would bar federal agencies, contractors, and grant recipients from procuring or using specified biotech equipment and/or services tied to foreign countries, potentially chilling partnerships, clinical trials, and data flows with Chinese firms. The 2025 version of the act adopts a softer tone (for example, it [omits explicitly naming WuXi companies](#)), but still introduces significant uncertainty for US sponsors planning China-related R&D.

Industry insiders worry about supply-chain exposure and innovation loss. Major stakeholders, such as Pfizer Chief Executive Albert Bourla, [publicly](#) stated that the US industry needs to [shift focus from trying to slow China’s progress](#) toward improving its own productivity and innovation, [calling for a stronger collaboration](#) between US and Chinese pharmaceutical sectors.

Results

[Concerns](#) were initially raised in 2024 that BIOSECURE-style legislation could [destabilize](#) the pharma industry. If enacted, the Senate measure could slow cross-border trials, limit access to diverse cohorts and cost-effective capacity, and delay deals as companies adopt a wait-and-see posture during NDAA reconciliation, raising timelines and costs especially for smaller sponsors. Senate passage signals bipartisan momentum even as details (scope, timelines, definitions) [remain to be finalized](#).

Lessons learned

The reintroduction of the BIOSECURE Act highlights the current challenges countries face in balancing national security with scientific progress. [Concurrent NIH restrictions on data-sharing](#) and projects with “countries of concern”, including curtailed Chinese access to NIH databases used for genetic-disease, disrupt international collaboration and ultimately lengthen timelines, delaying the delivery of essential medicines. [Policymakers are increasingly concerned that a major geopolitical conflict](#) with China could disrupt U.S. drug supply chains, causing widespread drug shortages.